

EFFECTIVENESS OF TOBACCO CESSATION PROGRAM IN PRIMARY
HEALTHCARE CENTERS IN LAHORE, PAKISTANAmmara Waqar^{*1}, Asad Tamiz ud Din², Hamid Mahmood³, Asif Hanif⁴, Amina Sajid⁵,
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⁸Imran.hanif@gdec.edu.pk, ⁹bilal.hassan@rsmi.uol.edu.pk, ¹⁰tahira.ashraf.biostats@gmail.com,DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18619422>**Keywords**Tobacco cessation, smoking,
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Abstract**Introduction:** According to the World Health Organization (WHO), smoking is the leading preventable cause of death worldwide. Currently, more than five million deaths per year are directly attributed to cigarette use, corresponding to approximately 10,000 deaths per day.² Additionally, the WHO reports that 600,000 people die each year due to passive smoking.**Methodology:** A prospective quantitative study was conducted in Basic Health Units with groups of 8 to 12 participants. Four sessions per month were carried out at the basic health units in Lahore to educate, motivate and provide necessary medication to support the smokers in tobacco cessation program. The healthcare professionals along with the physicians provided every help to the smokers in the cessation program. The program was fully supported by NHR&C, DRAP and ANF.**Result:** There was great acceptance and adherence of the program among the smokers in the first quartile the participation and adherence rate was more than 70% which continued in the second and third quartile the overall participation and adherence ratio was more than 62%.**Discussion:** The tobacco cessation program prove to be very effective as health professional, motivational speakers and family cooperated with the tobacco cessation team. The tobacco cessation program has produced tangible improvements in participants' lifestyles and health outcomes. Conclusion: It is recommended that the tobacco cessation program be expanded to all health units and maintained continuously within the municipality to promote public health and improve quality of life.

INTRODUCTION

Smoking is recognized as a chronic illness caused by dependence on nicotine and is therefore included in the WHO International Classification of Diseases (ICD-10). It is associated with high morbidity and mortality, being responsible for approximately five million deaths per year.¹

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), smoking is the leading preventable cause of death worldwide. Currently, more than five million deaths per year are directly attributed to cigarette use, corresponding to approximately 10,000 deaths per day.² Additionally, the WHO reports that 600,000 people die each year due to passive smoking.³

In Pakistan alone, around 200,000 people die from diseases directly related to tobacco. According to the Institute National Cancer Centre (INCA), more than 2,600 people die each year from illnesses related to passive smoking.⁴

More than 50 diseases are linked to smoking, many with high morbidity and mortality rates, including cancers (larynx, oesophagus, mouth), coronary heart disease (heart attack or angina), bronchitis, emphysema, aneurysms, digestive ulcers, respiratory infections, pregnancy complications, and male sexual impotence.⁵

Cigarette use not only affects individual health but also imposes a significant burden on society.

As stated, “Smoking generates a substantial economic burden for societies, characterized by the costs of medical care and loss of productivity due to morbidity and premature death.”⁶

Methodology

A prospective quantitative study was conducted in Basic Health Units with groups of 8 to 12 participants. All smokers participated in clinical sessions led by professional doctors and nurses. During these sessions, participants were assessed for the degree of nicotine dependence using the Fagerström Test, evaluated for risk of depression, and provided guidance on the program.

Four sessions per month were carried out at the basic health units in Lahore to educate, motivate and provide necessary medication to support the smokers in tobacco cessation program. The healthcare professionals along with the physicians provided every help to the smokers in the cessation program. The program was fully supported by NHR&C, DRAP and ANF. The program started from 1st January 2025 to 31st December 2025 for a period of 1 year. During that period 139 smokers were evaluated after the periods of 3 months to find out the validity of the program.

Results

Graphic 1. The evaluation of smoker every 4 months to evaluate the effectiveness of program.

Graph 1 : The first Quartile contains 41 smokers who participated in the tobacco cessation program

The effectiveness of the program can be seen that 56 smokers participated in the second quartile which shows the effectiveness of the program. In the 3rd quartile, the number of participant were 52 which means there was a decrease in the number of participant of the program.

Table 2 : It shows that the number of participants or participated in the cessation program were 22. Out of this number 18 smokers abundant or tried to quit smoking. There was increase in the number of smokers who try to quit or quitted in the second quartile but this number again dropped in the third quartile.

There was great acceptance and adherence of the program among the smokers in the first quartile the participation and adherence rate was more than 70% which continued in the second and third quartile the overall participation and adherence ratio was more than 62%. A similar study has been carried out by Oliveira et al., 2014. This study concluded

that the participation and adherence ratio in among the smoker was less than 60% (Oliveira et al., 2014).

Another study carried out by Paulina et al. (2016) for tobacco cessation program. There were 220 participant. The dropouts were 75 in the program. The participation to adherence was 61%.

Graphic 3 : Representing the three quartiles showing participants, dropouts and quitted.

Source: Lahore, Pakistan 2025.

Graphic 3 : Shows the success of tobacco cessation program in Lahore Pakistan it is worth mentioning here that the participants show there adherence to the program for 4 months. The number of smokers who quitted or almost 62% in the whole year.

Gaiotto et al studied tobacco cessation program. He concluded that it is important for the

smokers to continue tobacco cessation program for atleast 1 year with the support of healthcare professionals, motivation speakers and family.

Silva et al. (2013) carried out another study about the tobacco cessation program. His study concluded that the initial participation is always good in the program. It is upto healthcare professionals, motivation speakers and family

for support who support is of great importance

for the success of program.

Graphic 4 Demonstrate the use of medicines by the smokers of tobacco cessation program.

Source: Lahore, Pakistan 2025

The graph shows that 104 smokers participated in the program who want to quit but were unable to stop without medication. The nicotine dose of 7, 14, 21 mg and Bupropion were advised by the physicians and primary healthcare center to continue the tobacco cessation program. The success of the program has positive impact due to addition of medications.

Silva and Schneider (2013) concluded in a study that the use of medication increase the success of tobacco cessation program at the basic health units.

The implementation of the tobacco cessation clinics is an important step towards primary healthcare facilities in the rural population. The program gain success both in male and female.

Table 1: Gender and Smoking Outcomes

Gender	n	Adhered (%)	Quit Smoking (%)
Male	108	59	51
Female	31	68	61

The tobacco cessation program was for both male and female. The primary healthcare centers are situated in Lahore where urban and rural population use to visit. 108 male and 31 female participated in the program 59% male and 68%

female adherence to the program. 51% male and 61% female continued to adherence to the tobacco cessation program and were successful in quitting smoking.

Table 2: Outcomes by Medication Type

Medication Type	Adhered (%)	Success (%)
None	48	35
Nicotine 7 mg	63	52
Nicotine 14 mg	66	54

Nicotine 21 mg	68	56
Bupropion	70	60

The use of medicine seems to be very effective physically, mentally and emotionally. The people considered that they cannot quit without the support of medication, health professional support and family support. Smokers who do not use medication shows low adherence to the program. As the dose of nicotine increases from 7mg to 14mg, the success rate increases upto 67% in that participants. The dose of 21mg mg nicotine produces 72% adherence to the program. This study shows that the adherence to the program requires medications as a substitute for tobacco cessation program.

Discussion

Tobacco cessation program has been started keeping in view of the socio demographic profiles of the participants in Lahore Pakistan. The program has been started in the basic health units of Lahore Pakistan. The participants were both from the rural and urban areas of Lahore. A comprehensive, intersectoral, multi-disciplinary team was required to convince, motivate and adherence the smokers to the tobacco cessation program.⁷

Actions carried out by the NTCP include reducing advertising,⁸ running campaigns to encourage cessation,⁹ program implementation,¹⁰ training health professionals,¹¹ providing necessary medications,¹² offering psychosocial support, and operating a stop-smoking hotline, among other initiatives.

The NTCP includes a subprogram based on the Cognitive Behavioural Therapy Approach (CBTA), combined with pharmacotherapy, to improve access for smokers seeking to quit and to empower health professionals in Basic Health Units to assist smokers through intake and follow-up. This recommended model by the Ministry of Health is deployed across basic health units nationwide.¹³

The program comprises five approaches: brief/minimal, basic, specific/intensive,

relapse/lapse support, and interventions for non-smokers. Evidence shows that any duration of cognitive behavioural therapy increases abstinence rates; however, individual sessions cannot exceed 90 minutes. After clinical evaluation, smokers interested in quitting participate in structured sessions and follow-up maintenance sessions held every four months throughout the year.¹⁴

Sessions can be individual or in support groups of 10-15 participants, coordinated by one or two health professionals. Sessions with fewer than three participants are not recommended. The four initial sessions are preferably conducted weekly, followed by two biweekly maintenance sessions and a monthly open meeting with the entire group to prevent relapse over a year. Individuals with high nicotine dependence are provided medication.¹⁵

In CBT, the Ministry of Health provides pharmacological support to minimize withdrawal symptoms when CBT alone is insufficient. Commonly used medications include nicotine patches, chewing gum, and Bupropion tablets.¹⁶

In Lahore, Pakistan, the NTCP was launched in 2024 with the aim of establishing smoking cessation offices in 80% of Basic Health Units to assess smoker adherence and participation in cognitive behavioural therapy (CBT) and cessation programs.¹⁷

The tobacco cessation program prove to be very successful in terms of smokers participation, adherence and finally quitting the smoking. The cognitive behaviour therapy edit with non-pharmacological and pharmacological support prove to be very effective among smokers. The relapse and the dropout ratio was less as compare to program in which medication was given.¹⁸

The tobacco cessation program prove to be very effective as health professional, motivational speakers and family cooperated with the tobacco cessation team. The tobacco cessation program

has produced tangible improvements in participants' lifestyles and health outcomes.

Conclusion

It is recommended that the tobacco cessation program be expanded to all health units and maintained continuously within the municipality to promote public health and improve quality of life. The combination of behavioural and medicinal strategies has proven effective and should remain a central component of tobacco control efforts in Pakistan.

Institutional Review Board Statement

The study was conducted according to the guidelines of the Declaration of Helsinki and approved by the University of Lahore, Lahore Pakistan.

Informed Consent Statement

Written informed consent was obtained from all participants involved in the study.

Data Availability Statement

The raw data supporting the conclusions of this article will be made available by the authors on request. The data are not publicly available due to privacy and ethical reasons.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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Asif Hanif: Associate Researcher
Amina Sajid: Article review
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